

Mobility Ratio Measurements Across Collodion-coated Clay/Resin based Inorganic Complex Membranes

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Manuscript received 18 April 1973; revised 29 January 1975; accepted 13 March 1975

Mobility ratio measurements have been made by collodion coated and uncoated inorganic complex membranes based on clay or resin. The part played by collodion is discussed in terms of adsorption mechanism.

LING¹ observed the unlike behaviour of collodion coated glass electrode. Later, studies by Adhikari and Ghosh² showed that collodion coated clay membranes behaved to a limited extent as an ion-selective electrode. According to them, a layer of electrolyte and/or water between uncoated electrode surface and collodion played some role in the growth of membrane potential, which contradicts Bernstein's³ opinion of the gross permeability for membrane potential.

Here, different inorganic complexes impregnated on resin (Dowex 50 WX-8) and clay (Padegaon H-clay) are used as membrane material and the bi-ionic potential (B.I.P.) and hence the mobility ratio⁴ measurements are made using these membranes when they are collodion coated and when they are not coated. A comparison of their performance has been made to evaluate the part played by collodion on these membranes in development of B.I.Ps.

Materials and Methods

0.5 μ H-clay from Padegaon (predominantly montmorillonite 0-30 cm depth) soil was prepared by the usual method of sedimentation, dispersion, followed by dialysis. H-clay was exchanged with CuCl₂ to produce Cu-H-clay⁵. This Cu-H-clay was ground to 200 mesh size and was refluxed in waterbath for 8 to 10 hr with ammonia. The resultant material was filtered, dried, ground to 200 mesh size and formed into a membrane by mixing thoroughly 0.6 g of this material with 0.4 g of polystyrene, 10 ml of toluene, 1 drop of dibutylphthalate and evaporating resulting suspension on a plain stainless steel plate.

* Dowex 50 WX-8 resin was exchanged with CuCl₂ to form copper resin (Cu-R). The processes of reflux, drying, grinding were done with ammonia, ethylenediamine and formed into membranes following the aforesaid method.

The above membranes were cut into suitable sizes and affixed at the end of pyrex tubes by polystyrene/toluene affixer.

To obtain the coated membrane, one side (outside) of the membrane plate is coated with a 4% collodion (E. Merck) and excess collodion drained out. Thus a thin film of collodion gets sprayed over the membrane surface. The collodion-coated membranes are then washed with distilled water several times dried and exchanged with desired electrolyte solutions before making actual measurements. These coated membranes are referred to as unoxidized collodion coated membranes (C.m.).

Details of experimental procedure for mobility measurements were similar to those reported earlier⁶. For determination of Na/K mobility ratio, the two sides of the membrane were made reversible by keeping in contact with 0.1(N) solutions of respective ions. Washed thoroughly the solutions of known Na⁺, K⁺ ion activities were placed on two sides of the membrane. From the observed e.m.f. of the cell (i)

mobility ratio was calculated from the equation given below⁴

$$E_{B.I.P.} = \frac{RT}{F} \ln \frac{a_{K^+}}{a_{Na^+}} \cdot \frac{u_{K^+}}{u_{Na^+}}$$

or

$$E_{B.I.P.} = \frac{RT}{F} \ln \frac{u_{K^+}}{u_{Na^+}} \text{ for } a_{K^+} = a_{Na^+}$$

A plot is made for E_{B.I.P.} against outside KCl concentration and is shown in the Figure 1.

Results and Discussions

Results of measurements show that biionic potential $E_{B.I.P.}$ varies with the concentration of the outside KCl. For uncoated membrane it attains a maximum value at a concentration of 0.006N KCl and becomes practically independent of that concentration (Fig. 1). The corresponding $E_{B.I.P.}$ plots for coated membranes resemble those of uncoated one upto a certain concentration after which $E_{B.I.P.}$ values decrease with increase in outside KCl solution concentration (Fig. 1). The $E_{B.I.P.}$ values for coated and uncoated membranes for the same ion pair are also

Fig. 1

different. It may be that such difference is due to the extent of adsorption of K^+ from outside solution at the two different surfaces. The amount of electrolyte n adsorbed per unit surface area of the membrane may be related to surface charge density σ and surface potential E by Gouy⁷ relation $n = K\sigma$

$$= K' \sin h \frac{eE}{KT} \approx K' \frac{e}{KT} E \sqrt{C} \text{ (for low } E) \approx K_2 \sqrt{CE}$$

where C stands for salt concentration. If it is assumed that adsorption of electrolyte by membrane

surface obeys Langmuir type isotherm then

$$\sqrt{\frac{C}{E}} = \frac{1}{a} + \frac{b}{a}C$$

constants. In this latter equation E stands for the biionic potential of membranes for the ion pairs already stated. The plot of $\sqrt{C/E}$ against C are shown in the Fig. 2. The different adsorption isotherms for different membrane surfaces are obtained

Fig. 2

(adsorption maxima for the coated membranes have disappeared) which have different intercepts and slopes that are characteristic for each membrane surface. The shape also assumes Langmuir type isotherm. From this it is natural to assume that adsorption plays a major role in determining the difference in $E_{B.I.P.}$ for coated and uncoated membranes and electrical potential development across exchangeable interface.

References

1. G. N. LING, "Glass Electrodes Hydrogen and Other Cations", 1967, p. 284; *Chem. Abs.*, 1967, 67, 70227m.
2. M. ADHIKARI and D. GHOSH, *J. Inst. Chem. (India)*, 1973, 45, 172.
3. J. BERNSTEIN, *Arch. ges. Physiol.*, 1902, 92, 521.
4. C. E. MARSHALL, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1937, 43, 1158; 1948, 52, 1284.
5. A. N. BASU and S. K. MUKHERJEE, *J. Indian Soc. Soil Sci.*, 1966, 14, 91.
6. M. ADHIKARI and M. PAUL, *J. Appl. Polymer Sci.*, 1971, 14, 2675.
7. A. W. ADAMSON, "Physical Chemistry of Surfaces". Interscience, N.Y., 1967, p. 187.